

THE FACTOR OF ATTENTION AND CONCENTRATION IN THE PROCESS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

Manukyan A.

PhD, Associate Professor,

Khachatur Abovyan Armenian State Pedagogical University Yerevan, Armenia

Abstract

The article investigates the role of attention and concentration in the process of foreign language learning. It tries to prove that attention is tightly connected with learning, and, accordingly, learning is connected with attention. Instructional coaching implementation in the Armenian secondary education. The author defines the concept of attention and derives its types, as well as she points out the difficulties the learners may face when having their attention or concentration impacted or distracted. The article also suggests some solutions about learners' attention span.

Keywords: Attention span, types of attention, developing learners' concentration, attention, concentration, short term memory, long term memory.

Introduction. Human's mind is constantly attacked by huge amount of information every single second. According to biological researches, only our senses send over eleven million bits of information stimuli to our brain every second (eyes-10000000, skin-1000000, ears-100000, smell-100000, taste-1000). Yet, interestingly enough, when the researchers measured information processing capabilities during "intelligent" or "conscious" activities, such as reading or piano playing, they came up with a maximum capability of less than 50 bits per second. For example, a typical reading rate of 300 words per minute works out to about 5 words per second. Assuming an average of 5 characters per word and roughly 2 bits per character yields the aforementioned rate of 50 bits per second. Clearly, the exact number depends on various assumptions and could vary depending on the individual and the task being performed. To have this issue fixed scientists added a screening layer between input signals and Working Memory. The goal of this layer is to protect Working Memory from overload. It works like a filter. And this filter has a name - **Attention**.

Attention is a complex phenomenon that has been extensively studied for many years. Attention isn't a constant phenomenon. A person can change his attention span and intensity of attention depending on different situations. Attention has a preprogrammed priority system based on importance for survival and current

concerns. Internal signals like hunger, pain, fear and external ones like loud noise or a movement are related to danger and have the highest priority. These types of signals are the same for everyone. (1)

Attention and concentration is required to successfully complete a task and it is especially important when doing new activities. If our attention or concentration is impacted, we can have the following difficulties in your everyday life:

- Remembering information (if information is not initially 'stored' or 'filed' well in your brain, it is harder to recall later)
- Maintaining attention when reading e.g. forgetting what you have read straight away
- Forgetting to complete familiar tasks properly e.g. forgetting to add milk to a cup of tea
- Being easily distracted e.g. by people talking around you or the TV in the background
- Not finishing a task that you have started.

To deeply understand the concept of attention in learning process, it would be better first consider some types of attention. Different specialists derive different types of attention, but we will refer to Dr. V.S Gayathri, a certified dyslexia counselor, an educational therapist, who, in her article "Different types of Attention" gives 5 types of attention and proves them with examples about their implications. (3)

Types of Attention

<p>Focused Attention</p> <p>Example: Studying for an exam or working on a project.</p>	<p>Sustained Attention</p> <p>Example: Reading a book, watching a magic trick, or watching an interesting movie.</p>	<p>Selective Attention</p> <p>Listening to a conversation with a lot of surrounding noise and picking up certain parts.</p>	<p>Devided Attention</p> <p>Simultaneously concentrating on various factors like driving and holding a conversation simultaneously.</p>	<p>Alternating Attention</p> <p>Example: Teachers and parents excel in alternating attention.</p>
---	---	--	--	--

1. Focused Attention: This is when we are paying attention and not distracted by external stimuli. Here, people can channel their complete attention on a single task, and everything else is considered less important. It is also called **Executive attention** which blocks unimportant features of the environment. It is the attention we use when we are moving towards a particular end.

Example: Studying for an exam or working on a project.

2. Sustained Attention: It means concentrating on a certain time-consuming task. Holding attention over a period of time is necessary for the focus and concentration needed in learning, listening during lectures, or paying attention during conversations or instructions.

There are three stages of sustained attention which is called one Attention Span:

- **Paying Attention** – Where you start focusing.
- **Keeping Attention** – Where you sustain your attention.
- **Ending attention** – When you finally stop paying attention.

Once your attention ends, you will need time to focus again and remove distractions. Hence, you might notice that people get distracted and often leave the task incomplete, and return after they can refocus after some time. People can get better at sustained attention as they practice it.

Example: Reading a book, watching a magic trick, or watching an interesting movie. As reading requirements become more advanced in the older grades, sustained attention is challenged by chapter books and reading comprehension.

3. Selective Attention: It is when we block out certain features of our environment and focus on one particular feature. It means focusing on a single stimulus in a complex setting.

We must have the ability to focus on a particular message or object by filtering all background noise. But the problem is that people tend to neglect what is going

around (even if it's important). Hence, the message can easily be manipulated or misunderstood due to communication issues.

Consciously, and unconsciously, we are able to select the input which is most important. Having the ability to select from the many points of visual, auditory, interoceptive, and tactile stimuli in order to focus and attend to just one, is the brain's ability to select and respond to just one factor that matters most.

Example: Listening to a conversation with a lot of surrounding noise and picking up certain parts. This is because you are choosing to focus on this one person's voice, as opposed to other surrounding distractions like other's people voices. Another example can be a student listening to their teacher during a lesson while a lawn mower is running outside the classroom window.

4. Divided Attention: It refers to one's ability to focus on two or more things at the same time. Multitasking is not always an easy thing to manage. The ability to hold attention to various simultaneous points of concentration can require practice.

Some instances of divided attention are easier to manage than others. For example, texting while you are trying to talk to someone in front of you is much more difficult. For kids, it can be holding a conversation while they are playing. Age, agility, the degree of adaptation, and other factors impact this ability.

Example: Simultaneously concentrating on various factors like driving and holding a conversation simultaneously. Another example is talking to a friend on the phone while you're straightening up the house.

5. Alternating Attention: This refers to the ability to switch or immediately transfer focus from one activity to another. Switching points of concentration are needed to make sudden switches in alternating attention in tasks that require different cognitive skills.

Alternating attention requires the ability to use the other attention types in tasks. Here the mind should be flexible and quick to understand and translate every piece of information gathered.

Example: Teachers and parents excel in alternating attention.

Attentional Blink: According to a theory, attention is just like vision. When we try to visualize two targets at the same time, one of them appears sharp while the other one gets blurred. Similarly, when people focus on two targets at the same time, they tend to miss the second one. When these targets are linked with strong emotions, it becomes easier to reduce attention blink.

Attention allows us to plan or preview and monitor and regulate our thoughts and actions. Attention is the first step in the learning process. From a learning perspective, the information that we want to learn has to pass Sensory and Working memories and then be stored in Long-Term Memory. Only the information that has reached Long-Term Memory matters. Only this information can be considered learned.

As we considered above, without attention new information can't reach Working Memory or can't get enough computing time to be successfully processed. As a result, such information can't reach Long-Term Memory.

In other words, the input information that didn't get attention cannot be learned. So the main conclusion about the importance of attention is extremely simple – no attention, no learning.

Now we see that attention is tightly connected with learning, and, accordingly, learning is surely connected with attention. But is it equally so for foreign language learning? What benefits does attention have in foreign language learning? It is already stated by many scientists that people who are bilingual or trilingual they have much more developed attention span. Let us have a look at the recent studies. Dr. Thomas Bak (a lecturer at Edinburgh's School of Philosophy, Psychology and Language Sciences) shows that young adults proficient in two languages performed better on attention tests and had better concentration than those who spoke only one language. Dr. Bak tested 853 participants in 1947, when they were all 11 years old. They were retested in 2008 and 2010, when they were in their early 70s. He found that those who became bilingual performed better than expected. The strongest effects were seen in general intelligence and reading. The results showed that learning a new language in adulthood still has positive results, meaning there's never a reason to feel too old to gain the cognitive benefits of learning a new language. (4)

As we see above foreign language learning develops learners' concentration and attention, but as teachers we have also heard for hundreds of times that learners' attention span is short, so we should deliver the most important material in the first 20 minutes of the lesson, as learners can be distracted after that. To make our learners as concentrated as possible, here are some tips we can use during the lessons:

Include Physical Activities

Nowadays there are so many learners who struggle with attention. They often do better if they are given brief breaks for active play. Taking a break can help the attention-challenged students stay focused. Starting with 15 minutes of active play before a challenging task can also help a child stay more engaged.

Remove Visual Distractions

When learners are struggling with a difficult task, clutter in the classroom or on the desk can make it impossible to keep their brain where it needs to be. We should remove unnecessary clutter and visual experiences from the workspace which will give the learners fewer excuses for not focusing on the task at hand.

Break Tasks into Pieces

If we break tasks into smaller chunks, the learners focus long enough to perform the task, then take a break, and then come back to successfully finish it. Sometimes learners show a better performance with this strategy rather than finishing the task in one sitting.

Conclusion. Attention is the key aspect of learning. It's a provider for new knowledge from the environment to our permanent memory. Without attention, we are simply not able to learn. (6)

Our brain and the remembering process are difficult things. But thanks to schematic simplifications like Information Processing Model we can get a basic understanding of our brain organization, how it works, its features and limitations. As students, this knowledge may help us increase learning efficiency by developing good study habits. And as learning designers, to create more effective educational products.

Because attention plays such a significant role in learning, it should become one of the basic metrics of learning products and teachers' effectiveness. Attention is like a muscle: the more you use it, the better it gets.

References

1. <https://www.britannica.com/science/information-theory/Physiology>
2. <https://metronorth.health.qld.gov.au/rbwh/wp-content/uploads/sites/2/2017/06/ot-attention-and-concentration.pdf>
3. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/different-types-attention-dr-v-s-gayathri/>
4. <https://www.whitbyschool.org/passionforlearning/learning-a-new-language-helps-brain-development>
5. Gass, S. M. (1988). Integrating research areas: A framework for second language studies. *Applied linguistics*, 9(2), 198-217.
6. Schmidt, R. W. (1990). The role of consciousness in second language learning. *Applied linguistics*, 11(2), 129-158.
7. Zeidan, F., Johnson, S. K., Diamond, B. J., David, Z., & Goolkasian, P. (2010). Mindfulness meditation improves cognition: Evidence of brief mental training. *Consciousness and Cognition*, 19(2), 597-605.